

UV curable coating for flame-retardant textile finishing

W. Phomsook¹ and N. Jiratumnukul^{*1,2}

¹ Department of Materials Science, Faculty of Science, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

² Research Unit of Advance Ceramic and Polymeric Materials, National Center of Excellence for Petroleum, Petrochemicals and Advance Materials, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand 10330.

* Corresponding author (nantanaj@gmail.com)

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1 Introduction

One of the important finishing in the textile industry is a flame-retardant finishing. Flame-retardant fabrics are commonly used in home textiles in order to retard the flame spreading and reduce the damage of properties and lives when fire accident occurs. Flame retardant agents such as halogen-containing compounds and phosphorous-containing compounds are popularly used. In textile finishing industry, the technique of pad-dry-cure with heating process is mostly used. However, this pad-dry-cure technique has disadvantages in that it requires long curing time and high energy consumption. To solve this problem, many researches involved in using radiation curing technique in finishing process [1-2]. Radiation curing technique has several advantages in that it helps reduction of solvent emission and imparts high productivity in curing process to obtain dried films [4]. The phosphorous-containing monomers are popularly used as flame retardants for UV curing system because they are environmental friendly flame retardants [5-6]. The flammability of fabric depends on main composition of resin used in finished coating and the formation of charred crust during the fabric combustion [7-8]. The main objective of this study is to prepare a flame retardant UV-curable coating formulation and finish onto polyester fabric to obtain flame retardant property polyester fabric.

Experimental

2.1 Materials and Reagents

Polyester fabric (223 g/m²) was purchased from Paknam Textile Company, Bangkok, Thailand. UV curable oligomer was purchased from Cytec Industries (Thailand) Co.,Ltd. Phosphorous-containing (P-containing acrylate) was purchased from A.C.S. Xenon Ltd., Bangkok, Thailand. Photo-

initiator as 2-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1-phenyl-propan-1-one was purchased from Ciba Specialty Chemicals (Thailand) Co.,Ltd. Ethyl alcohol was purchased from Lab scan Analytical Sciences, Bangkok, Thailand

2.2 Flame retardant UV-curable coating formulations

Curable coating formulations were prepared with different weight ratio of monomers. Photo-initiator as 2-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1-phenyl-propan-1-one was mixed in the formulation with the amount of 3% by weight. The formulation was diluted with ethyl alcohol 27% by weight. The well-mixed formulations were then applied onto the fabric.

Table 1. Formulation of UV-curable coating

Formula	Weight Ratio	
	Acrylate oligomer	P-containing acrylate
0% P-containing acrylate	70	0
10% P-containing acrylate	60	10
30% P-containing acrylate	40	30
50% P-containing acrylate	20	50

2.3 Fabric Finishing

Unfinished Polyester fabric was soaked in coating solution for 1 minute and passed into padding machine to obtain 60% pick up of coating materials. Finished fabric was then passed through UV chamber to obtain dried finished fabric on both sides.

2.4 Coating weight on fabric

Coating weight on the fabric were determined by weighing and calculated %add-on using the following equation.

$$\% \text{ Add-on} = \frac{(\text{Weight of finished fabric} - \text{Weight of unfinished fabric})}{\text{Weight of unfinished fabric}} \times 100$$

2.5 Determination of Limiting Oxygen Index

Finished fabrics were evaluated the value of Limiting Oxygen Index on PL Limiting Oxygen Index tester (Stanton Redcroft, UK) according to ASTM D 2863-06a [8].

2.6 Determination of characteristic of fabric burning

Flame retardant property of finished fabrics was tested using Atlas 45⁰ Automatic Flammability Tester according to ASTM D1230-94 [9].

2.7 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The cured film sample (100 micron) was prepared on a glass plate. The cured film was taken from the glass plate and undergone the thermal analysis using TGA/SDTA851 (Mettler Toledo, Switzerland). The heating condition was from 25-800⁰C with heating rate of 10⁰C/min under N₂ atmosphere.

2.8 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy was used to investigate the surface of finished fabric and char residue after burning. SEM JEOL JSM-6400 was used in the study.

2.9 Laundering procedure

Finished fabric was washed with 4 g/L of ECE detergent (liquor ratio 1:30) at 40⁰C for 30 minutes by Gyrowash machine (James H. Heal & Co.Ltd.)

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Coating weight on finished fabric

Prepared UV-curable coating formulations consist of acrylate oligomer and P-containing acrylate as main compositions. Both chemicals have acrylate functional group that can be polymerized using

photoinitiator to initiate the reaction under UV-radiation. In order to control the amount of coating film on finished fabrics, the prepared coating formulations were applied on the fabric with 60% pick up using padding machine.

The %add-on of finished fabric before and after a laundry cycle were calculated and shown in Table 2. From the result it was found that after a cycle laundering %add-on of coatings decreased due to residue monomers were removed from the finished fabrics. Moreover, coating formulation with high amount of acrylate oligomer remained somewhat high after passing a laundry cycle. This result indicated that high acrylate oligomer formulations provide more fully cured coating film than those of high P-containing acrylate monomers.

Table 2. %Add-on of finished fabric before and after laundering

Formula	%Add on	
	Before laundering	After laundering
0% P-containing acrylate	53.43	49.42
10% P-containing acrylate	46.81	43.56
30% P-containing acrylate	49.61	34.98
50% P-containing acrylate	53.12	24.21

3.2 Flame retardancy

Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI) tester was used to evaluate the performance of flame retardancy of the finished fabrics. The value of LOI indicates the minimum concentration of oxygen required in burning. The percentage volume of oxygen concentration (%LOI) was reported. The high %LOI means the better flame retardant performance. It was found that %LOI increased as the amount of P-containing acrylate in the coating formulations increased as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The value of Limiting Oxygen Index of finished fabric before and after a laundry cycle

The %LOI of unlaundered fabric increased from 18.5 to 26.4 as the amount of P-containing acrylate increased from 0% to 50%. After the finished fabric was laundered and %LOI were taken, it was found that the %LOI did not increase as it did in unlaundered finished fabric. The %LOI of laundry fabric increased from 18.5 to 22.8 relative to the %LOI of unlaundered fabric. However, the %LOI of laundered finished fabric were higher than 21, which is a minimum requirement of oxygen index in burning. This can be explained that the higher amount of P-containing acrylate in the coating formulation at 30% and 50% might be excess levels and these excess amounts were removed from coating surface by laundering. As a result, the lower %LOI was observed.

Atlas 45⁰ automatic flammability was used to investigate the flammability performance of finished fabric by ignition a flame on the testing fabric for 5 seconds and monitor the flame spreading and burning behavior of the fabric.

The burning characteristic of finished fabric after passing a laundry cycle was observed relative to unfinished fabric. The images of fabric after burning were taken and shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Photograph of the characteristic of burning fabric after a laundry cycle from Atlas 45⁰ Automatic Flammability Testing.

After the flame was ignited on the unfinished fabric, the flame spread out along the length of the piece of fabric and it took 26 seconds till the flame extinguished. Unfinished fabric presented 3-4 molten droplets from burning fabric while all other finished fabric did not present molten droplets. The finished fabrics, passed a laundry cycle, were examined their behaviors as a function of the amount of P-containing acrylate in the coating formulations. As the amount of P-containing acrylate in the coating formulations increased, the spreading time and burning area of fabric decreased. The fabric, finished with 10%P-containing acrylate, showed larger burning area relative to those finished with 30% and 50%, respectively. It can be seen that the fabric finished with 30% and 50% provided a spot-like burning area and they took around 10 seconds burning and then self-extinguished. In this 10 seconds burning time, it was included 5 seconds of ignition time.

3.3 Thermal stability of the UV-cured film

Thermogravimetric analysis technique (TGA) was employed to investigate the amount of char residue. UV-cured film with 100 micron thickness was prepared on glass plate and then was taken to investigate using TGA under nitrogen atmosphere. The 50%P-containing acrylate UV-cured film was analyzed relative to 0%P-containing acrylate UV-cured film. The result is shown in Figure 3. and

Figure 4. It was found that the 0%P-containing acrylate UV-cured film did not have any residual weight of cured film sample left after it was heated till the temperature of 471.5 °C. However, the TGA result of 50%P-containing acrylate UV-cured film provided more residual weight of 41.6% at the same heating temperature of 471.5 °C. Moreover, the 50%P-containing acrylate UV-cured film remained providing char residue even it was heated till 800 °C. These results confirm that P-containing acrylate monomer was important in char formation. The formation of char at high temperature can decrease spreading out of burning area of coated material which correlated to the results of burning characteristic of finished fabric as shown in Figure 2, and also correlated with %LOI investigation.

Figure 3. Thermogravimetry curves of the (0% P-containing acrylate) UV cured film.

Figure 4. Thermogravimetry curves of the (50% P-containing acrylate) UV cured film.

3.4 Surface microstructure of finished fabric

UV-curable coating is a technique to initiate monomer to be cured film on a substrate. Properties of UV-cured film depends on main composition in the formulation and the formation of film on surface of substrate. The fully cured film of coating will show good performance of functional coatings. The SEM technique was used to observed the surface of finished fabric relative to unfinished fabric. The results are shown in Figure 5.

a) Unfinished fabric

b) 0%P-containing acrylate

c) 10%P-containing acrylate

d) 30%P-containing acrylate

e) 50%P-containing acrylate

Figure 5. SEM images of the unfinished fabric (a) and the finished fabrics (b,c,d and e)

According to the SEM analysis, Unfinished was observed the underlain fibers. It was found that the

underlain fibers was clearly visible and covered coating film was not observed. However, the covered coating film can be observed on the surface of all other finished fabrics and the underlain fibers of finished fabric was not clearly visible as it was in unfinished fabric. Therefore, this indicated that UV-curable system can be used to finish the polyester fabric to provide the flame retardant property.

4. Conclusion

UV-curable flame retardant coating for polyester finishing was successfully prepared. Flame retardant coating can be embedded onto fabric and provided good flame retardancy. After the finished fabric was passed laundry cycle the flame retardancy performance remained. Finished fabric with 50% P-containing acrylate showed high value of %LOI (26.4%). However, after laundry cycle %LOI slightly decreased to 22.8%. Flame retardant property of finished fabric depends on the amount of phosphorous-containing monomer in the coating formulation in that the higher the amount of P-containing monomer in the coating the better the flame retardancy.

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